

GO-BACK-N ARQ APPROACH FOR IDENTIFICATION AND REPAIRING FRAME IN TRANSMISSION DATA

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ABSTRACT

The process of sending data in a vulnerable network such thing damage or errors that occur due to several factors such as noise, interference or also tissue factor unfavorable, Go-Back-N is a method of mechanisms controlling this error referred as Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ) , Effects ARQ is to change the data path that is not reliably reliable, the processes analyzed by Go-Back-N form of the transmission time of the frame, when the transmission/reply, propagation speed (slow, medium or fast), the time interval 'timeout' on timekeeper source and the number of frames to be transmitted.

Keyword: ARQ, Automatic Repeat Request, Go-Back-N, Frame, Transmission Time, Noise Network Correction

1. INTRODUCTION

Generating Data were [1] sent as a sequence of frames, the frames arrive by the same command when sent, and each frame that is transmitted change and a variable amount of delay before it reaches the receiver [2]. Errors that may occur is the loss of frame (so that the frame failed to be accepted receiver) and damage to the frame (frame admittedly has arrived, but some bits have errors, so the receiver rejected it) [3] [4] [5].

The most common technique for controlling the error is error detection [2], positive reply (returns a positive reply to the frame error-free is received well), retransmission after the time is up (source retransmit frames unanswered after a certain moment) and responses negatively and retransmission (returns a negative reply to the frame are detected encountered an error. Sources retransmit the damaged frames) [2] [6] [3]. This error control mechanism called Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ). ARQ effect of this is to change the data path is not reliably be reliable, this research uses the method of Go-Back-N ARQ as an error checking method in data transmission [4].

2. THEORIES

Basic usefulness of the communication system is running the exchange of data between the two parties [7] [8]. An example is the exchange of voice signals between two phones on the same network. Key elements of communication models [7] [8] are:

- a. Source
This tool generates data so that it can transmit, for example, a phone and a PC (Personal Computer).
- b. Transmitter (Sender)
Often the data generated from the source system is not transmitted directly in its original form. A transmitter is quite moving, and marking information in the same way as generate signals electro-magnetic that can transmit over multiple sequential transmission systems. For example, a modem duty to deliver a digital bit stream from a device that has already prepared such as a PC, and transform bit stream into an analog signal that can traverse over the telephone network.
- c. Transmission System (Transmission System)
In the form of a single transmission line or a complex network that connects the source to the destination.
- d. Receiver (Receiver)
The receiver receives signals from transportation system and incorporates it into a specific shape that can be captured by the goal. For example, a modem will receive an analog signal coming from the network or the transmission path and converting it into a digital bit streams.
- e. Destination (Destination)
Capturing data generated by the receiver.

Figure 1. Overview of Communication Model

Source and transmitter (sender) is part of the origin system, while the receiver (receiver) and the destination (goal) is part of the purpose, process of transmission/delivery of detailed data can be seen in the figure below,

Figure 2. Details of the data transmission process

Think of it as the input device and the transmitter is a component of a PC, the user intends to send a message m to another user. Users activate the electronic mail program on the PC and enter the message via a keyboard (input device). A string of characters briefly detained in main memory. PC connected with some transmission medium, such as a local network or telephone network, through an i/o device (transmitter) in this case, a local network or modem transceiver. Data transfer to the transmitter as a series of voltage change which indicates bit - bit on the communication bus or cable. Transmitter connected directly to the media and changed the flow of the incoming signal can be transmitted [7] [8].

The transmitted signal is delivered to the media be subject to some disorders before it reaches the receiver. Thus, the received signal may be different from the source. The receiver will attempt to analyze the authenticity of the origin data, based on the received signal and knowledge of the media and produce a series of bits [2] [1] [3]. This bit is sent to the computer output, where bits - these bits briefly detained in memory. In some cases, the destination system will attempt to alert when an error occurs and to cooperate further with the source system to finally get the data free of errors (error-free data). This data provided to the user via an output device, such as a printer or monitor. Messages or message are seen by the user is usually a copy of the original message [4] [7] [8].

2.1 Data Link Control

Data Link Control is the control layer on any communication device that provides functions such as flow control, error detection and error control [2] [8] communication between two transmission stations-receiver connection directly, there are several requirements for effective communication [2] [8]:

- a. Frame synchronization: data sent in blocks called frames. The beginning and end of each frame must be identified first.
- b. Flow control: the sending station must not send frames at the rate/pace faster than the receiving station that can absorb it.
- c. Error control: bits error generated by the transmission system must be improved.
- d. Addressing: the multipoint line, the identity of the two stations that are within a transmission should be known.
- e. Control and data on the same link: usually not desirable to have a separate communication path for control signals. Therefore, the receiver must be able to distinguish the control information from the data being transmitted.
- f. Link management: starters, maintenance, and termination of the exchange of data require coordination and cooperation among the stations.

2.2 Flow Control

Flow Control is a process used to set the rate of data transmission between two nodes to avoid sending data too fast compared with the slow data reception [2] [6] [7] [8]. Flow Control is mainly used to avoid bottlenecks by adjusting the data rate or speed of data between the sending host and the receiving host. So node that accepts not flooded with data from transmission node for data that is sent too fast [2] [6] [7] [8].

2.3 Go-Back-N ARQ

Go-back-N ARQ is a form of error control based on the sliding window flow control techniques. In this method, the source station can send a frame rows are sorted based on a modulo number [6] [9]. The number of replies current frame is determined by the size of the window, using the technique of the sliding window flow control. In the event of a fault, the destination station will reply (RR = Receive Ready) frames that come in as usual. When the target station detects an error in a frame, the destination station sends a negative reply (REJ = Reject) to the frame. Destination Station then discards the frame and all the frames that will be coming up with errors in the frame received correctly. Thus, the source station, when it receives an REJ, must retransmit the frame with errors in it plus all additional frame is transmitted while [9]. Below is the working process of Go-Bank-N ARQ

Figure 3. Go-Back-N Working Process

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this method, the source station can send a frame rows are sorted based on a modulo number. This method uses the sliding window flow control techniques. In the event of a fault, the destination station will reply (RR = Receive Ready) frames that come in as usual. When the target station detects an error in a frame, the destination station sends a negative reply (REJ = Reject) to the frame. Destination Station then discards the frame and all the frames that will be coming up with errors in the frame received correctly. Thus, the source station, when it receives an REJ, must retransmit the frame with errors in it plus all additional frame while transmitted. To more clearly understand this method, consider the following example, the window size = seven frames and frame numbering starts from 0 to 7, based on methods Go-Back-N ARQ the processes will look like the following picture

Figure 4. Sending Frame From Source To Destination

A source based image 4 consists of seven pieces of frames (F0, F1, F7), then of the frame provided delivered F0, F1 and F3 to destination B, B sends RR3 (reply which states ready to accept F3), window borders and advance to the F3 and F2 window widened ahead because the window size = 7 frames.

A receiving RR3 and bounds forward in the front window and the window F3 F2 for widened front window size = 7 frames.

Figure 5. RR and REJ Process

B sends RR6 (ready to receive a reply stating F6), window borders and forward in front of the window wide to F6 and F5 forward because the window size = 7 frames.

A continues to send F6, F7, F0 and F1 so that the window shrinks up in front of F2.

Figure 6. Frame F0, F1 until F7 Received

The process described earlier will be repeated so that all the frames in the packet sent their full and well received by the receiver until there is no longer a damaged frame.

4. CONCLUSION

Methods Go-Back-N process error check on each frame that is sent by way of repeating until all the frames are delivered in good condition, in this process the receiver will send a status LOST or DAMAGE, research on ARQ has been much discussed and for the future could be tested to compare methods such as Stop and Wait ARQ, Go-Back-N and Selective-Reject ARQ.

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